

AIDAinnova

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PRODUCTION WITH INDUSTRY OF SMALL-SIZE μ -RWELLS

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Abstract:

The challenges posed by forthcoming High-Energy Physics experiments, require the development of particle detection technologies easily engineered and compatible with industrial-scale production. The micro-RWELL, a resistive Micro-Pattern-Gaseous-Detector based on sequential build-up technology, effectively meets these demands. This report addresses the technology transfer of the micro-RWELL detector to ELTOS SpA, an industry specialized in Printed Circuit Board manufacturing.

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Executive summary

This report provides a comprehensive overview of the transfer of the μ -RWELL manufacturing in an industrial framework. The introduction underlines the need to develop detector technology easily adaptable to industry, aiming at cost reduction and mass production, especially in view of the future challenges in High-Energy Physics. The μ -RWELL technology, developed at the Frascati National Laboratory, is then described in the subsequent section with the evolution towards layouts for high-rate applications. The report continues with a detailed description of the manufacturing phases: from the design of the components at LNF, passing by the construction at ELTOS SpA, the industrial partner of the project, to the finalization of the detector at CERN-EP-DT Micro-Pattern-Technology (MPT) Workshop. A particular focus is made on the commissioning of the sputtering machine to produce the DLC foils, one of the main components of the μ -RWELL detector. The results of the tests carried out with an X-ray gun at LNF and particle beams at the CERN North Area beam facility are then discussed in detail. Preliminary outcomes of the co-production pilot test performed in 2023 are summarized, indicating a production yield of approximately 80%. The fruitful experience gained in this phase of the technology transfer is a first step towards the construction of larger detectors as envisaged for the upgrade of the Muon system of LHCb.

1. INTRODUCTION

Muon detection systems in High-Energy Physics (HEP) experiments are typically positioned at a considerable distance from the primary interaction vertex, downstream of all other sub-detectors. This spatial arrangement is primarily attributed to the distinctive characteristics of muons, which traverse the entire experimental apparatus, requiring the implementation of extensive detection systems. The most suitable devices for constructing such large muon systems are gaseous detectors, characterized by robustness, cost-effectiveness, and hardly any size limitation. In recent years, in the framework of the RD51 worldwide collaboration [1], there have been remarkable advancements in Micro-Pattern Gaseous Detectors (MPGDs), resulting in the development of various new detector types with impressive performance: spatial resolution around 50 μm , time resolution between 5-10 ns, 97-98% efficiency, rate capability up to 10 MHz/cm² and radiation tolerance of the order of 1 C/cm². Notably, two well-established MPGD technologies, Gas Electron Multipliers (GEM) [2] and MicroMegas [3], have played pivotal roles in substantial upgrades to muon stations in the CMS [4] and ATLAS [5] experiments. The excellent spatial and time resolutions of MPGDs make them ideal particle trackers, enabling the reconstruction of tracks at distances of the order of several meters from the interaction region with sub-millimeter precision. MPGDs employ materials and manufacturing procedures extensively used in Printed Circuit Board (PCB) production, offering the distinct advantage of cost-effective and scalable production by the industry.

One particularly innovative MPGD, the micro-Resistive WELL (μ -RWELL) [6,7], based on sequential build-up (SBU) technology, has been proposed for the upgrade of the innermost part of the muon system in the LHCb apparatus [8]. This endeavor involves the production of approximately 600 detectors with an active area ranging from 250x300 mm² up to 300x650 mm². The μ -RWELL is also under consideration as a candidate for constructing the large muon system of the IDEA apparatus for the Future electron-positron Circular Collider (FCC-ee) [9], where thousands of detectors are foreseen. Over the years, from the introduction of the first prototype by the LNF-DDG (Detector Development Group), μ -RWELLS have been manufactured at the CERN-EP-DT MPT Workshop. Given the foreseen large-scale production requirements for LHCb and the potential application of this technology in FCC-ee, it has become imperative to move the production of the detector to the industry.

In this context, we are currently engaged in a technology transfer (TT) of specific manufacturing steps of the detector to ELTOS SpA, an Italian company specialized in PCB manufacturing [10]. ELTOS has a large experience in the construction of MPGDs, including technologies such as Thick GEM (THGEM) [11] and MicroMegas. The involvement of private industries in this R&D opens the way for the extensive adoption of μ -RWELL technology across various fields of application, ranging from HEP to industrial, medical, and homeland security domains.

2. THE μ -RWELL

The μ -RWELL is a resistive MPGD composed of two PCBs: a PCB acting as the cathode, defining the gas detector gap, and the μ -RWELL_PCB that couples in a unique structure the electron amplification and the readout stages, as shown in Fig. 2.1. A 50 μm thick polyimide (APICAL) foil, copper clad on the top side and sputtered with DLC [12] on the bottom side, is coupled to a standard PCB readout board, through a 50 μm thick pre-preg foil. The thickness of the DLC layer (typically in the range 10÷100 nm) is adjusted according to the desired surface resistivity value (50÷100 $\text{M}\Omega/\text{square}$) to provide discharge suppression as well as current evacuation. A chemical etching process of the polyimide foil is performed on the top surface of the overall structure to create a GEM-like matrix of truncated cones with 70 μm (50 μm) top (bottom) diameter and 140 μm pitch. This pattern constitutes the amplification stage. The high voltage applied between the copper and the resistive DLC layers produces the required electric field within the WELLS that is necessary to develop charge amplification, Fig. 2.2. The signal is capacitively induced on the strips/pads on the readout board [13]. The introduction of the resistive layer allows to achieve large gas gains up to 10^4 with a single amplification stage, while partially reducing the capability to withstand high particle fluxes [14].

Fig.2.1: Basic layout of a μ -RWELL.

Fig.2.2: Principle of operation of the μ -RWELL.

3. THE HIGH-RATE LAYOUTS

The simplest scheme for the evacuation of the current in a μ -RWELL is based on a single resistive layer with a grounding line all around the active area, Fig. 3.1, (Single-Resistive layout - SRL).

Fig.3.1: Sketch of the low-rate layout based on the SRL grounding scheme.

For large-area devices, the path of current-to-ground may become long and highly dependent on the point of particle incidence. To mitigate this effect, the solution is to minimize the average path towards the ground connection by introducing a high-density grounding network on the resistive stage. During our R&D, various high-rate (HR) layouts with dense grounding schemes have been implemented [15]: the Double-Resistive Layer (DRL), the Silver-Grid (SG), and the Pattern-Etching-Plating (PEP). In this document, we will focus on the two most recent PEP layouts: PEP-Groove and PEP-DOT, co-produced by ELTOS and CERN under the supervision of INFN-LNF.

Fig.3.2: General sketch of the high-rate layout based on the PEP grounding scheme

The PEP-Groove layout, Fig. 3.2 and 3.3, is a synthesis of the high-rate versions of the μ -RWELL (DRL and SG layouts). The ground connection of the DLC is performed with conductive grooves, 9 mm pitch, by etching from the top Cu layer, down to the DLC, and through the APICAL foil. The distance from the first amplification well to the PEP ground line (DOCA) [16] is about 600 μ m, corresponding to a global dead zone of the detector of approximately 20%. In Fig. 3.4 and 3.5 further details of the layout are shown.

Fig.3.3: Sketch of the PEP-Groove layout, with the definition of the main geometrical parameters.

Fig.3.4: Metallographic cross-section of the PEP-Groove layout.

Fig. 3.5: Picture showing the detail of the PEP-Groove layout. The conductive groove runs across the active area.

In the PEP-DOT layout, Fig. 3.6, the ground connection of the DLC is established by creating metalized vias from the top Cu layer through the DLC, down to the pad-readout of the PCB. The upgrade from the Groove version to the DOT one has significantly reduced the dead zone to 2-3%. In Fig. 3.7 and 3.8 further details of the PEP-DOT layout are reported, while in Tab. 3.1 the main geometrical parameters of these layouts are summarized.

Fig.3.6: Sketch of the PEP-DOT layout

Fig.3.7: Metallographic cross-section of the PEP-DOT layout.

Fig.3.8: Picture of the DOT-vias for the DLC grounding

Tab. 3.1: Comparison of the geometrical parameters of the PEP-Groove and PEP-DOT layout.

PEP type	DLC-GND pitch (mm)	Dead Zone (mm)	GND width (mm)	Insulation gap (mm)	DOCA (mm)
Groove	9	1.1	0.35	0.28	0.6
DOT	9	1.1	0.6	0.25	0.7

4. THE μ -RWELL MANUFACTURING

In the initial two years of the project, we convened multiple collaborative meetings involving representatives from INFN-LNF, the CERN-EP-DT MPT Workshop and ELTOS. During these meetings, we outlined a roadmap for the task, Fig.4.1, which encompassed eight key stages in the manufacturing process of the μ -RWELL_PCB:

1. Design of the detector at LNF
2. DLC sputtering on the backplane of the APICAL
3. Production of PCB readout (pad/strip patterned)
4. DLC patterning
5. DLC foil gluing on PCB
6. Creation of the PEP structure
7. Amplification stage patterning by APICAL etching
8. Electrical cleaning in dry atmosphere

The second step, previously conducted by the Be-sputter Company in Japan, is scheduled to be transferred to CERN, leveraging the CERN-INFN DLC (C.I.D.) sputtering machine operational from the beginning of 2023. In the initial phase, ELTOS focused on the preliminary standalone testing of manufacturing steps 3-4-5, while the responsibility for steps 6-7-8 remained with the CERN-EP-DT MPT Workshop. Under the supervision of the INFN-LNF scientific partner, ELTOS and CERN jointly produced numerous prototypes with different sizes and readout patterns. These prototypes were developed as part of the high-rate layouts within the scope of the R&D for LHCb upgrade. The 100x100 mm² μ -RWELL prototypes, featuring 9x9 mm² pad readout, are based on the new PEP layout. This approach offers several advantages with respect to the previous high-rate layouts. Prototypes have been characterized at LNF using a high-intensity X-ray gun to measure the gas gain curve and rate capability. Additionally, at the CERN SPS, a comprehensive X-Y efficiency mapping of the detectors has been performed.

Fig. 4.1: flow-chart of the manufacturing process of a μ -RWELL PCB.

4.1. OPERATIVE EXPERIENCE

The first step of the detector production involves the electronic CAD design of the μ -RWELL_PCB. This task is under the responsibility of the INFN-LNF electronic design service (SEA). Technical aspects are discussed in advance with experts from the CERN-EP-DT MPT Workshop as well as the technical managers of PCB production at ELTOS. The remaining two components of the detector, the cathode and the frame, are then designed by LNF-DDG. In Fig. 4.2 and 4.3 drawings for the various detector components produced by ELTOS are reported.

Fig. 4.2: Top (left) and bottom (right) drawings of the 100x100 mm² PEP-DOT layout with (9x9 mm²) pad readout.

Fig. 4.3: 3D drawings of components used to close the 100x100 mm² detector: the cathode (left) and the frame made of PEEK (right).

It is worth noticing that the detector, composed of few components, has a very simple structure. In addition, being designed to be openable, it allows interventions in case of need (i.e., for cleaning/washing).

4.2. DLC SPUTTERING

Apart from the design phase, the initial step that marks the real start of the detector manufacturing process involves the production of the fundamental component of the detector amplification stage. The base material for this component is a 50 μm thick APICAL foil supplied by the manufacturer with a 5 μm thick copper film applied to one side. On the opposite side of the APICAL foil, a thin layer of DLC is deposited. The deposition of the DLC is performed using the CERN-INFN DLC facility, a DC magnetron sputtering machine (built by AURION Anlagentechnik GmbH, Seligenstadt,

Germany) installed at CERN. This facility has been co-funded by CERN and INFN. In Fig. 4.4 some details of the magnetron sputtering machine are shown.

Fig. 4.4: The magnetron sputtering facility installed at the CERN-EP-DT MPT Workshop.

In a magnetron sputtering machine the material to be deposited on the substrate is provided by a target (Fig. 4.5 left) installed on a negatively charged support (cathode). A gas discharge (plasma) is ignited in the inert gas, in most cases an Argon-based mixture, present between the target and the substrate. The ions are accelerated towards the negatively charged target and strike out atoms due to impulse transmission. Magnets behind the target increase the extraction efficiency, focusing the ions on the target. The extracted atoms diffuse into the vacuum chamber and condense on the substrate as a thin layer. In addition, secondary electrons are released sustaining the gas discharge (avalanche).

The magnetron sputtering machine at CERN has five target holders: two fixed targets in the innermost part of the vacuum chamber and three removable targets accessible from outside (Fig. 4.5 right). The machine hosts a substrate support (drum): the company provided two drums to host flexible substrates with dimensions up to $1.7 \times 0.6 \text{ m}^2$ and rigid substrate up to $0.2 \times 0.6 \text{ m}^2$. The machine can be operated spinning the drum for a whole revolution or in oscillation mode around a given phase and with a properly set oscillation angle. In order to operate the chamber for the sputtering of different material, the system is equipped with three gas lines (Ar, O₂, C₂H₂) and each gas flow is governed by a MKS mass flow controller. The DLC is a metastable amorphous carbon. We know that carbon in nature can be found under different forms (graphite, diamond, fullerene) each characterized by the bonds created among the atoms, in particular sp² for graphite and sp³ for diamond. DLC is a mix of these two states resulting in a material with remarkable mechanical properties that justify its use in a large number of industrial applications.

Fig. 4.6 Ternary phase diagram of the DLC formation with respect to sp², sp³ and H content.

The ternary phase diagram (Fig. 4.6) published in [16] provides an idea of the quite complicated scenario related to the DLC formation, as even hydrogenated alloys (a-C:H) can be included in the film. Several studies have been published to understand the composition of the DLC as a function of the production technique (ion deposition, ion assisted sputtering, sputtering, cathodic vacuum arc, plasma deposition, pulsed laser deposition), and consequently to better realize the mechanical features of the film. In parallel the studies on the electrical properties underline how the different deposition parameters have a huge effect on the final surface resistivity of the film, which can range from few k Ω /sq. to G Ω /sq [17].

The resistivity needed to build the μ -RWELL detector must be between 50 and 100 M Ω /sq. Because of an annealing factor of about 2.5 when the sputtered base material is pressed on the PCB readout

the target resistivity should then be between 125 and 250 $M\Omega/sq$. It has been then necessary to start some dedicated scans on the deposition parameters of the sputtering machine. To save time the tests have been performed in oscillation mode ($\pm 25^\circ$ around the zero phase) on three $0.15 \times 0.15 \text{ m}^2$ APICAL samples stuck along the height of the cylinder (Fig. 3.5 right). Beside each sample, small $1.5 \times 1.5 \text{ cm}^2$ glasses have been placed for the evaluation of the DLC thickness. The APICAL foils underwent a heating treatment before the sputtering (at least 16 hours at 100°C) to lower as much as possible the humidity present in this material.

Fig. 4.7: Tests with Ar/N plasma: the effect of the nitrogen amount (left) and the effect of the plasma pressure at a given percentage of N_2 (right).

The first tests have been focused to understand the effect of an Ar/ N_2 plasma on the resistivity of the coating. Among the several parameters beyond the sputtering process, we investigated the percentage of the nitrogen with respect to the Argon flux at the process pressure of 2×10^{-3} mbar and a further scan has been done at a given nitrogen flux changing the pressure of the plasma (Fig. 4.7). It is clear from these plots that to obtain the target resistivity the amount of nitrogen, leaving the other parameters unchanged, would be too large. A second test campaign has been done substituting the nitrogen with acetylene (C_2H_2) and the results look quite promising (Fig. 4.8), since with a much lower gas flux it is possible to achieve the desired resistivity (the left-right plots differ on the power dissipated by the power supply on the cathode, moreover there is the possibility to act on the deposition time).

An open question on this procedure is the stability in time of the DLC resistivity. One sample from each run has been baked at 220°C for 2 hours to monitor how the resistivity changes after a thermal shock (the same treatment that each foil will suffer when pressed and glued on the PCB board for the production of the detector). While for the Ar/ N_2 tests this shock affected the resistivity increasing it by a factor between two and ten, with acetylene the values are halved. The measurement of the resistivity many days after the deposition and the thermal treatment resulted in a remarkable drift with nitrogen, differently from the acetylene case where we observed very stable values. In order to improve the sputtering uniformity along the cylinder height in early November 2023 some tests have been dedicated to this purpose, with a unique sample of about $0.1 \times 0.6 \text{ m}^2$. A 0.5 mm thick aluminum mask, properly bent, has been stuck by Kapton tape on the shutter in front of the graphite target (Fig. 4.9-left). The principle behind this test lies in the fact that the resistivity is proportional to the inverse of the thickness, so sputtering less in the central part of the sample should level the resistivity to the

values obtained at the edges. The effect is shown in Fig. 4.9 right: the resistivity is contained in a belt of 25 M Ω /sq. around an average value of 225 M Ω /sq. (about 10%) along a region nearly 50 cm wide. Once overcome this issue, the future tests will involve sputtering of large size APICAL foils (1x0.6 m²) in order to be ready for the production of the final detectors.

Fig. 4.8: Tests with Ar/C₂H₂ plasma: resistivity against acetylene amount at 2 kW (left) and 1 kW (right) power dissipated on the cathode.

Fig. 4.9: Picture of the aluminum mask (left) and its effect of the aluminum mask on the uniformity of the resistivity (right).

4.3. MANUFACTURING PROCESS IN ELTOS

After the deposition of the DLC on the APICAL foil (herein referred to as the “DLC foil”, or simply “DLC”), the manufacturing process moves to ELTOS.

The readout PCB

The readout PCBs, Fig. 4.10, of the μ -RWELL detectors are produced by ELTOS typically with a FR4 thickness of 1.6 mm or 3.2 mm. These PCBs are the base on which the amplification stage of

the detector is integrated. The μ -RWELL_PCB is a rigid-flexible multi-layer PCB: the rigid part is composed of the PCB-readout, which can be suitably segmented into pads, strips, or pixels, while the flexible part is formed by the DLC foil. The PCB readout is manufactured using conventional photolithographic techniques.

Fig. 4.10: a typical 2x2 PCB-readout produced by ELTOS.

The DLC patterning

The DLC foil, before being properly coupled to the PCB, requires a suitable patterning. The DLC material must be removed everywhere except in the region that will serve as the active area of the detector. This area corresponds to the portion of the PCB where the readout electrodes are created (up to now only pad PCB is considered).

The process is performed as follows:

1. A layer of photoresist is applied to the DLC, which is coupled to a rigid FR4 support (Fig. 4.11 (left)). Subsequently, it is exposed to UV light using a Direct Imaging UV machine (Fig. 4.11 (center))
2. The photoresist is developed to be removed from the entire surface, except in the areas where the DLC is intended to remain (Fig. 4.11 (right))
3. The DLC is then subjected to a brushing machine to selectively remove the excess of DLC material (Fig. 4.12)

Fig. 4.11: DLC foil lamination with photo-resist film (left); UV exposure of the photo-resist by means of a Direct Imaging UV machine (center); DLC foil after photo-resist developing (right).

Fig. 4.12: the DLC foil at the end of the patterning process, ready to be glued onto the readout PCB.

The gluing of the DLC foil on the readout PCB

The final set of manufacturing operations conducted at ELTOS involves the gluing of the DLC to the readout PCB. This process is achieved by using a thin sheet of prepreg, specifically the PANASONIC R-1551W type 106. The gluing is carried out in a press, with a cycle lasting approximately 8 hours, at a temperature of 210 °C and a pressure of 180 N/cm².

The sequence for preparing the DLC/prepreg/readout PCB sandwich is the following:

1. The surface of the readout PCB is cleaned with an anti-static roller (Fig. 4.13 - left)
2. The prepreg is carefully positioned on the PCB (Fig. 4.13 - center)
3. The DLC is aligned on the sandwich (Fig. 4.13 - right)

Fig. 4.13: the main steps of the sequence for the preparation of the μ -RWELL_PCB.

The sandwich is then inserted between layers of anti-stick sheets (Pacothane) and anti-conformant sheets (Pacoflex). This layering process ensures that the APICAL remains perfectly flat and does not conform to the profile of the pad (or strip) pattern on the readout PCB. This is required by the subsequent chemical etching processes for the realization of the amplification stage of the detector (performed at CERN). Fig. 4.14 shows the details of the stacking placed inside the press, while fig. 4.15 shows the press employed for the coupling of the DLC to the readout PCB.

Fig. 4.14: sketch of the stacking used for the coupling of the DLC foil to the readout PCB.

Fig. 4.15: press facility used for the coupling of the DLC foil to the readout PCB

Once the manufacturing operations at ELTOS are complete, the μ -RWELL_PCBs are shipped to CERN for finalization. At the CERN-EP-DT MPT Workshop, the following photolithographic processes are carried out (the etching process of the APICAL is under patent):

1. The creation of the DLC grounding network is achieved using the PEP technique (sec. 3). This process requires the masking of the rest of the PCB.
2. The WELL pattern on the copper layer of the PCB plane is created. This process requires the masking of the PEP DLC grounding network.
3. The APICAL undergoes a chemical etching process using the copper hole pattern as a mask, resulting in the creation of amplification wells.

The detector manufacturing is eventually completed and ready for the “electrical hot cleaning”. This conditioning process involves a gradual voltage increase, up to 670V. Carried out in a dry atmosphere at $T=90^{\circ}\text{C}$, this operation cannot last less than 24 hours. At the end of the test the good detectors have a residual dark current of a few nA. Detectors that do not pass electrical cleaning, depending on the severity of the problem, are washed at high pressure with demineralized water while, in the most serious cases, undergo a light chemical etching of the copper and then subjected to electrical cleaning again.

Upon completion of these procedures, the detector is ready for characterization and testing at the LNF-DDG laboratory and, if necessary, for further beam test at CERN.

5. CHARACTERIZATION AND TEST OF PROTOTYPES

The characterization and performance of the detector, including the gas gain, rate capability, efficiency, timing and tracking performance, are evaluated by X-ray at LNF and by particle beam facilities at CERN or at PSI.

5.1. X-RAY CHARACTERIZATION

A first characterization of the μ -RWELL prototypes is carried out at a high-intensity 5.9 keV X-ray gun facility (Fig. 5.1). Common measurements include the gas gain curve and rate capability.

Fig. 5.1: Picture of the 5.9 X-ray gun (PW2217/20).

The gas gain curves for the PEP-Groove and PEP-DOT are shown in Fig. 5.2 and 5.3 respectively: a typical gas gain of the order of 10^4 has been achieved for both layouts.

Fig. 5.2: Gas gain curve of the PEP-Groove.

Fig.5.3: Gas gain curve of the PEP-DOT

For rate capability measurements, we have used several 2 mm thick lead collimators with hole diameters ranging from 1 to 5 cm to define the X-ray spot. Detectors have been equipped with a 100 μ m thick Kapton window (Fig. 5.4), while a copper-clad Kapton foil has worked as the cathode. The use of light cathode and window instead of the usual FR4 PCB helps minimizing X-ray absorption before reaching the drift gap.

Fig. 5.4: Detector installed in the X-ray box. Detail of the Kapton window and cathode used for rate capability measurement.

The normalized gas gain curves of the PEP-Groove and DOT layouts as a function of X-ray flux for various irradiation spots are presented in Fig. 5.5 and 5.6, respectively. These measurements have been performed at a gas gain of 4000, with detectors operated using $\text{Ar}:\text{CO}_2:\text{CF}_4 = 45:15:40$.

Fig. 5.5: Rate capability of the PEP-Groove layout for different lead collimators

Since the irradiated area is larger than the DLC grounding pitch (approximately 1 cm for both layouts), the gain drop is, as expected, almost independent of the spot size. The rate capability, defined as the rate corresponding to a gain drop of 10%, is of the order of several MHz/cm² for both layouts.

Fig. 5.6: Rate capability of the PEP-DOT layout for different lead collimators.

5.2. TEST BEAM RESULTS

The comparison between the two high-rate layouts has been continued through a dedicated beam test at the CERN North Area with a pion beam of about 150 GeV/c. The test setup has included an external 2D tracking system, for the evaluation of the efficiency. A detailed investigation of the DLC-grounding area, which introduces a dead zone in both detectors, has been carried out.

Fig. 5.7: Global efficiency of the PEP-Groove and PEP-DOT

By irradiating the detectors with a muon beam spot size of approximately $3 \times 3 \text{ cm}^2$ (FWHM), we can assess the overall impact of dead zones on detection efficiency. In fig. 5.7, we present a comparison of the overall efficiency of the two layouts as a function of the HV applied to the amplification stage, at a drift field of 3.5 kV/cm. The PEP-Groove layout exhibits an overall efficiency of approximately 80%, whereas the PEP-DOT layout shows a nearly negligible inefficiency.

Fig.5.8: 2D efficiency map of the PEP-Groove layout (left) and PEP-DOT layout (right). Red circles indicate the DLC-grounding zones implemented as a 'groove' on the PEP-Groove and a 'dot' on the PEP-DOT layout, resulting in lower-efficiency areas.

By exploiting the tracking capability of the setup, we have produced a two-dimensional efficiency map for the two layouts. In fig. 5.8 we report the 2D efficiency map for the PEP-Groove (left) and for the PEP-DOT (right). Red circles highlight low efficiency zones corresponding to the DLC-grounding connections. The efficiency profile across the DLC grounding zones is presented in Fig. 5.9: on the left an efficiency drop of approximately 30-40% for the PEP-Groove; on the right a drop less than 10% for the PEP-DOT. Outside the grounding connections the efficiency plateau is larger than 95% for both layouts, Fig. 5.10.

Fig. 5.9: Efficiency profile of the PEP-Groove layout (left), and PEP-DOT layout (right) close to their DLC-grounding connections.

Fig. 5.10: Efficiency of the PEP-Groove and PEP-DOT measured outside the dead-zones.

6. PILOT CO-PRODUCTION TEST

In 2023, a pilot co-production test of detectors was performed at ELTOS. Following the developed manufacturing procedure, sixteen 100x100 mm² detectors with PEP-DOT layout have been built, fig. 6.1. The main difference between the various detectors produced is the thickness of the prepreg layer used to glue the DLC foil to the PCB readout. The smaller the thickness of the prepreg the greater the charge induced on the readout. The study of this effect, outside the scope of this project, will be performed in the near future.

At the moment, eleven detectors have been delivered. Of the remaining five, four are under the electrical cleaning procedure. Fig. 6.2 shows the gas gain curves of ten of the eleven delivered detectors. Additional details are outlined in Table 6.1. A preliminary production yield of about 90% has been achieved for the delivered detector batch.

Fig.6.1: Detectors co-produced by ELTOS and CERN-EP-DT MPT Workshop.

Fig. 6.2: Gas gain curve for the detectors co-produced by ELTOS and CERN Workshop.

Tab. 6.1: Technical specifications of the co-produced detector batch

Detector #	Prepreg type	DLC resistivity	Production status	Max HV/Gain	comments
106_1	1x 106		Cleaning		@ CERN
106_2	1x 106	7.5	Delivered	640/10000	
106_3	1x 106		Cleaning		@ CERN
106_4	1x 106	7	Delivered	640/9500	
1080_1	1x1080		Cleaning		@ CERN
1080_2	1x1080	4.8	Delivered	630/6700	
1080_3	1x1080	5	Delivered	n.a.	short
1080_4	1x1080		Cleaning		@ CERN
2x106_1	2x106	35	Delivered	660/16000	
2x106_2	2x106	37	Delivered	650/13000	
2x106_3	2x106	35	Delivered	670/15000	
2x106_4	2x106	34	Delivered	650/12500	
2x1080_1	2x1080	33	Delivered	670/19500	
2x1080_2	2x1080	110	Delivered	680/19000	

2x1080_3	2x1080	44	Delivered	680/19000	
2x1080_4	2x1080		To be delivered		@ CERN

7. CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

The future challenges of high energy physics experiments require detectors based on simple, reliable and easily engineering technology in order to be produced by industry.

The μ -RWELL detector, a single-amplification stage resistive MPGD, meets these requirements. The objective of the work carried out within the framework of the task 7.3.2 of the AIDAInnova project is to transfer a substantial portion of the construction to the industry working in the field of PCB manufacturing. The chosen industrial partner for this endeavor is ELTOS SpA, an Italian company.

This report provides an overview of the detector characteristics, outlines the design and testing steps performed at INFN-LNF, and offers a schematic description of the construction processes conducted at ELTOS and CERN-EP-DT MPT Workshop.

The report summarizes the results of characterization tests and performance measurements done at INFN-LNF and at the CERN North Area beam facility. The experience described in this report indicates that a significant part of the detector construction can be effectively carried out by industry, offering substantial advantages in terms of production time and cost-effectiveness. Indeed, the successful production, shared between CERN and ELTOS, of 16 prototypes with $100 \times 100 \text{ mm}^2$ active area, has confirmed the possibility to achieve this technology transfer. Next step will involve the construction of large area detectors, particularly those planned for the LHCb muon system upgrade.

Finally, it is essential to highlight the significant effort ongoing in the production of large DLC foils, a fundamental component of the detector amplification stage. The acquisition of the DC-magnetron sputtering machine, a fruitful joint venture between CERN and INFN, is a crucial development, allowing a remarkable advancement in this technology.

8. REFERENCES

- [1] <https://rd51-public.web.cern.ch/>
- [2] F. Sauli, GEM: A new concept for electron amplification in gas detectors, Nucl. Instr. and Meth. A 386 (1997) 531-534.
- [3] Y. Giomataris et al., MICROMEAS: a high-granularity position-sensitive gaseous detector for high particle-flux environments, Nucl. Instr. and Meth. A 376 (1996) 29-35.
- [4] The CMS Collaboration, The Phase-2 Upgrade of the CMS Muon Detectors Technical Design Report, CERN-LHCC-2017-012 / CMS-TDR-016, 22 October 2018.
- [5] The Muon ATLAS Collaboration, The New Small Wheel Upgrade Project of the ATLAS Experiment, Nuclear and Particle Physics Proceedings, Volumes 273–275, April–June 2016, Pages 1160-1165.
- [6] G. Bencivenni et al., The micro-Resistive WELL detector: a compact spark-protected single amplification-stage MPGD, JINST 10 (2015) P02008.
- [7] G. Bencivenni et al., The μ -RWELL layouts for high particle rate, JINST 14 (2019) P05014.
- [8] The LHCb Collaboration, Framework TDR for the LHCb Upgrade II, CERN/LHCC 2021-012, LHCb TDR 12, 24 February 2022.
- [9] A. Abada et al., FCC-ee: The Lepton Collider, Eur. Phys. J. Special Topics 228, 261-623 (2019)
- [10] <https://eltos.com/>
- [11] R. Chechik et al., ThickGEM-like hole multipliers: properties and possible applications, Nucl. Instr. and Meth. A 535(2004)303.
- [12] A. Ochi et al., Carbon sputtering Technology for MPDG detectors, Proceeding of Science (TIPP2014) 351.
- [13] M.S. Dixit, A. Rankin, Simulating the charge dispersion phenomena in Micro Pattern Gas Detectors with a resistive anode, Nucl. Instr. and Meth. A 566 (2006) 281–285.
- [14] G. Bencivenni et al., The μ -RWELL layouts for high particle rate, JINST 14 (2019) P05014.
- [15] G. Bencivenni et al., The state of art of the μ -RWELL technology, JINST 18 (2023) C08014.
- [16] W. Jacob, W. Moeller, On the structure of thin hydrocarbon films, Appl. Phys. Lett. 63, 1771–1773 (1993).
- [17] N. Ohtake et al., Properties and Classification of Diamond-Like Carbon Films, Materials 2021, 14, 315.

ANNEX: GLOSSARY

Acronym	Definition
MPGD	Micro-Pattern-Gaseous-Detector
GEM	Gas-Electron-Multiplier
μ -RWELL	micro-Resistive WELL
DLC	Diamond-Like-Carbon
DOCA	Distance of Closest Approach